

Long Term Data Issues: Workshop about Preservation, Archiving and Access in the NFDI

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Introduction

Research data is an asset for future research. In many fields of science, it will be reproduced and validated in new contexts, re-used and cited. Good research data practice supporting these activities was proposed by Wilkinson et al. as the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) (Wilkinson et al. 2016). On the other hand, digital objects such as research data are often fleeting, subject to changing technological solutions, software and standards, to hardware failure, human error, defunding of institutions, bit-rot, link-rot and more. Digital preservation aims to prevent loss of information and therefore to preserve digital objects over long periods of time, i. e. maintaining the long-term FAIRness of data. The German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (RfII) recognized digital preservation as an important topic for NFDI (German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures 2016) and while many digital preservation standards (ISO14721, ISO16363, ISO16919, DIN31644), best practices (e. g. CoreTrustSeal certification (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2022), nestor seal certification (nestor Certification Working Group 2025) and solutions (e. g. tools documented in COPTR¹) exist, implementation of digital preservation in the NFDI still raises many questions.

The NFDI working group Long-term access and preservation (LTA) (Markus, Leinen, and Stäcker 2025) organized a workshop with the title "Long Term Data Issues: Workshop about Preservation, Archiving and Access in the NFDI" on November 6th 2024, in order to discuss relevant and pressing questions with NFDI consortia as well as involved and associated institutions. The workshop started with an introduction of digital preservation (Markus 2024), followed by presentations of digital preservation activities in NFDI consortia NFDI4Culture, NFDI4CS, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Microbiota, FAIRAgro and NFDI4Objects (Arnold et al. 2024) and discussion of the topics "selection criteria", "data volumes", "preservation of research software", "long-term responsibility" and "initiatives, networking" in breakout rooms. The following sections contain central points from the breakout room discussions, as well as short conclusions for each topic.

¹ Community Owned digital Preservation Tool Registry (COPTR)
https://web.archive.org/web/20250327050233/https://coptr.digipres.org/index.php/Main_Page

Selection criteria

The goal of the session "selection criteria" was to discuss how to approach the question of appraisal² of research data for long-term preservation. The decision to preserve research data for the future beyond a retention period of 10 years, potentially indefinitely, is always combined with a short-term as well as a long-term cost and resource allocation. Considering the fast growing amount of research data being created, it is essential to (re)appraise the lasting value of research data and decide what data to preserve and what data can be disposed of.

Beginning with a conversation about the status quo on the appraisal question in different disciplines, the group was in agreement that there is a widespread uncertainty in the scientific communities on what data to preserve as well as how to approach an appraisal process. Furthermore, no established archival standard or clearly defined criteria for the appraisal of research data is available. While specific issues vary in the disciplines (e.g. in some, scientists need to be convinced that their data might be of lasting value, in others, the sheer volume of data poses a significant challenge), the overarching necessity for guidance and support on the topic became clear. This includes guidance on a generic as well as on a more domain- and datatype-oriented level.

Another topic discussed was the question of responsibility for the appraisal of research data for long-term preservation between data producers (e.g. researcher) and the archive as the curating institution of the data in the long term. On the one hand the decision about what data is being accepted, ingested and preserved in the digital archive lies ultimately at the curating institution. On the other hand the appraisal of research data requires domain- and datatype-specific expertise in order to understand and assess the lasting value as well as the domain-specific relevance and importance of the data. Thus, appraisal is ideally conducted in an inclusive dialogue-based process between the stakeholders. This raises the question though, what a sustainable business model could look like considering the human resource allocation required for such an appraisal process. Furthermore, awareness and understanding of the difference between publishing data and securing the long-term preservation of digital research data needs to be increased.

In conclusion, the group sees the need for support in the scientific communities in the following areas:

- Raising awareness about the importance and challenges of appraisal and providing guidance on abstract formal and content-related criteria for an appraisal process.

² Appraisal means in this context the evaluation and assessment of the lasting value of data as a basis for the decision process, which data to keep and preserve and which data to dispose of.

- Establishing standards for the appraisal of research data. Here the outcomes of the recently started project "EOSC EDEN Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level"³ as well as the proposed nestor working group "nestor-Archivstandard zur Bewertung von Forschungsdaten"⁴ could be promising.
- Clarifying responsibilities and establishing sustainable business and funding models for long-term preservation of research data, including the appraisal of the lasting value of research data.
- Providing guidance and support for domain- and datatype-specific considerations in the appraisal process.

Data volumes

The group discussing huge data volumes quickly came to realise that the meaning of “huge” depends on the discipline you are part of. Astrophysics, remote sensing, climate simulation, and medicine are examples of data-intensive research branches. Unlike other disciplines, they often have to worry about how to transfer data to the person or place that needs them, because internet bandwidth is insufficient. A scientist recently noted on Mastodon that sending 0.5 petabytes on 40 SSD drives from the US to India by plane (a 28 hour trip) results in a competitive bandwidth of 24.52 gigabit per second.

Another issue is more common among most fields of science: how to identify the significant parts of the recorded data and how to extract them in the best way. Large-scale storage often lacks means of standard analysis. XML is an ordinary example: most processing languages need to load the complete XML dataset for parsing - but what to do if the XML input exceeds a regular machine’s memory? Actively preserving research data with its semantics and reproducing scientific work are processes that both rely heavily on those or similar analytical means.

On the other hand, the need for reproducibility varies, even inside the data-intensive realm. Fluid engineers or data or materials scientists using simulations often respond that reproducibility is unnecessary since future computing environments will give finer results anyway - and discard a lot after two to four years. Only samples of their input data are kept alongside the source code of the simulation inspected, as annexes of their research papers.

Others, like earth or climate science, keep a lot more for a lot longer. We raised a hypothesis that retention schedules in a scientific field often rely rather on vague assumptions than on informed decisions. Similar biases might exist regarding “lossy” compression of data content. But informed decisions exist: astronomers seem to have reached agreement on what is unnecessary noise in astronomical signals (Offringa 2016).

³ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250328154027/https://eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-eden/>

⁴

https://web.archive.org/web/20250214114400/https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/DE/Arbeitsgruppen/AG_Archivstandard/2025ausschreibungArchivstandard.html

Of course, the large scale data centers of science use tiered storage systems and the medium of choice for the rarely-used bulk of data is tape. In common practice, their physical lifetime is a crucial factor for the survival of their virtual load. Most large scale data lives as long as their carrier because transferring data from large compounds of tape libraries to the next generation is time-consuming and costly. Every five to ten years, economic reasons for appraisal come up.

All persons involved in the discussion knew the phenomenon of orphaned data left behind by guests or retired persons. One single means of regulation emerged in conversation several times: money, to pay the keepers and to maintain the repository.

In conclusion:

Large volumes do not necessarily need long term retention, but some do.

Large volumes prove challenging when analysing and interpreting data for reproducibility and preservation.

Keeping large volumes means high budget requirements.

Keepers of large volumes do not necessarily do intense research on efficient retention periods.

Preservation of research software

The session “preservation of research software” aimed to discuss how to preserve software and how to preserve it better than today.

Research software increasingly needs to be preserved, as it also becomes more relevant in research and, respectively, in the NFDI. It is central for reusability and reproducibility of research output (models or data) as most research data have been processed at some point by scripts or software. Yet, preservation of software, specifically preservation of software reusability is complex as software in itself is often complex. Complexity is not due to the code itself, as it usually exists as text but due to high amounts of dependencies, changes in the dependencies and frequent changes in the code itself, i. e. updates and respective versioning.

In digital preservation, preservation of software has a tradition as e. g. computer game museums preserve access to and usability of computer games by maintaining old hardware or emulating computer environments. Additionally, emulation is one of the established preservation measures in digital preservation. On the other hand, the amount of research software, tools or scripts with various (documented or undocumented) dependencies might not scale in this context - emulation environments have to be maintained as well and the amount of specific environments necessary for every kind of archived script and software might be beyond a preservation department's, institution's or museum's ability.

Beyond the question of long-term software reusability, other challenges arise like publication, storage and bitstream preservation of software, as well as findability of software and software versions.

And even further, best practices and solutions may differ for complex open source software, proprietary software and simple scripts or code fragments.

There are several initiatives targeting various aspects in this context, among them:

- Prominently, the Software Heritage Initiative which collects and stores public code from various sources on the internet (github, gitlab, etc.) in the Software Heritage archive, using a system agnostic data model⁵.
- Software Sustainability Institute⁶
- Software Preservation Network⁷
- Emulation as a Service infrastructure⁸
- Software Management Plans (SMPs) (Grossmann et al. 2024)
- FAIR4RS Principles (Chue Hong et al. 2022)

Four topics (2-5) were discussed during the session, as well as NFDIxCS activities (1):

1 NFDIxCS activities and positions (see also slides Arnold et al. 2024)

- NFDIxCS is targeting less research replication and more data reusability as there is a difference between reusing data and replicating data (using software).
- They are working on conceptual problems, specifically maintaining privacy, e. g. when analyzing sensitive data with software.
- They are using the Software Heritage (SH) archive. University Duisburg-Essen are setting up a mirror for the SH archive which is not yet public.
- Proprietary software is a general problem as Software Heritage archives only publicly available code.
- There is no direct overlap between emulation and NFDIxCS structures, since Emulation as a service (EaaS) has a different focus. EaaS focuses more on older systems.
- NFDIxCS is interested in feedback from other areas within NFDI regarding standards for preservation of software.

2 Preservation of additional material alongside code

Additional material includes e. g. dependencies, context information, computer environments, issues and discussions, wikis etc.

- Additional material may be preserved via Docker container. It is recommended to preserve also the binary (docker container) and not just the construction plan/the code.

⁵ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250319001816/https://docs.softwareheritage.org/devel/swh-model/index.html>

⁶ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250306212833/https://www.software.ac.uk/>

⁷ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250323132037/https://www.softwarepreservationnetwork.org/>

⁸

<https://web.archive.org/web/20250306223520/https://www.softwarepreservationnetwork.org/emulation-as-a-service-infrastructure/>

- A solution specific for preserving additional material of git-projects can be CoSAI. It generates a package from a git project including not just code but also the respective wiki, github issues etc. (Cooper and Rampin 2022; Rampin 2024).

3 Findability, reusability

- The Software Heritage archive allows looking up code versions and also dependencies from e. g. 10 years ago which helps to reconstruct the original environment.
- Often findability is insufficient and details are missing e. g. in projects where code is already available (Galaxy project contains bioinformatics code, in EOSC node there are already software artifacts available). The same applies to data driven software and LLMs.
- Recommendation: add a Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) to software.
- Recommendation: Virtualization/emulation with QEMU⁹
- Reusability of disc images and software contained in disc images is often limited. Solutions for linking disc images to the respective computer environments is still an open question but the PREMIS Data Dictionary may support this (PREMIS Editorial Committee 2015).

4 Citing and referencing of software

- How to prove that the used/referenced software is the right one?
- Software should be referenced in Archival Information Packages (AIPs) with the correct version and with an identifier, e. g. the Software Heritage identifier
- There are various proposals for developing standards for citing software.

5 Role of local archives

- How to combine existing initiatives in this context is still an open question and may be a political question.
- There is no overarching plan at the moment, but there's potential for subdivision of labor.
- Applies to e. g.
 - state funded initiatives, archives (states in Germany)
 - NFDI and national archives
 - supercomputing centers, e.g. Jülich
 - GWDG Göttingen
 - EU, GAIA-X
 - ...

The discussion emphasized potential to improve not only solutions for preservation of software but also inclusion of already existing initiatives which are tackling various specific questions. Digital preservation aims for long-term reusability but it seems unclear how that can be achieved for research data at scale

The group was interested to continue working on the topic.

⁹ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250323114621/https://www.qemu.org/>

- One option for more in-depth discussion would be a workshop on the topic of software preservation.
- Additional options were increasing information exchange and networking via a mailing list on this topic and how existing initiatives fit into the respective approach.
- initiating contact with international initiatives (e. g. Software Preservation Network, Software Sustainability Institute).

These potential steps to proceed will be raised in the NFDI WG LTA but further work may depend on time and resources of the working group members.

Long-term responsibility

The session on “Long-term responsibility” focused on how to organize responsibility for long term preservation, especially beyond the lifetime of individual projects, employment contracts and funding streams. The starting point was the observation that, on the one hand, repositories are expected to be responsible for data stewardship, e. g. according to the TRUST principles (Lin et al. 2020), while, on the other hand, a significant number of research data repositories fail and shut down (see e. g. Strecker et al. 2023).

Three main challenges were discussed during the session:

- Most research and infrastructure relies on public funding, but it is difficult to ensure a continuous flow of funding for long-term tasks. One reason is the variety of channels and actors with differing responsibilities and priorities. Another challenge is the disconnect and the temporal gap between those who create data, those who fund or invest in data preservation and those who would use the data in the future. The main beneficiaries of specific reusable research data are usually not yet present to articulate their demand.
- A coordination or division of labor for preservation tasks is often useful and necessary (e. g. between a computer center and another institution). However, in some cases, it can complicate processes and increase costs to distribute tasks, such as documentation and metadata tasks when domain-specific knowledge is required.
- Repositories should be expected to have an exit strategy and successorship management (see for example the corresponding criteria in the nestor seal of approval (nestor Certification Working Group 2025)). But it can be challenging to transfer certain datasets and the responsibility for them to other institutions. Certain rights and contracts might be non transferable, or the missions of repositories might diverge in such a way that a repository cannot justify taking on all responsibilities for all datasets of the original repository.

As a result the session formulated some expectations and ideas regarding what should or could be done in the NFDI:

- Foster a common understanding, shared expectations and standards for long-term preservation services (while acknowledging that one-size-fits-all solutions are unrealistic due to inevitable exceptions).
- Clarify responsibilities and raise awareness.
- Clarify funding for infrastructure and address the backlog of currently unarchived research data.

Initiatives and networking

The session on initiatives and networking discussed how to connect LTA-initiatives and enhance networking. The aim is an effective distribution of labour regarding digital preservation in NFDI (including relevant business models), avoiding redundant activities in various initiatives and connecting experts. On the other hand, initiating and maintaining contact requires resources as well. Generating an overview of relevant initiatives and discussing funding and business models should reevaluate WG LTA tasks, possible next steps and may help with focusing efforts.

Existing initiatives

- DINI/nestor working group research data¹⁰
- nestor working group SIP concretization¹¹
- EOSC task force Long-Term Data Retention¹²
- CoreTrustSeal Research Data Alliance (RDA) group¹³
- Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC)¹⁴
- Open Preservation Foundation (OPF)¹⁵
- Digital Curation Centre (DCC)¹⁶
- Federal state initiatives for LTA, e. g. *Digitale Langzeitarchivierung an den Hochschulen in NRW (LZA.NRW)*¹⁷

Information exchange possibilities at conferences or due to meeting invitations

- Cordi conference (26-28 August 2025)
- e-Science Tage
- nestor meetings
- RDM groups/initiatives

¹⁰

https://web.archive.org/web/20240611073629/https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Arbeitsgruppen/AG_Forschungsdaten/ag_forschungsdaten_node.html

¹¹

https://web.archive.org/web/20240611075124/https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Arbeitsgruppen/AG_SIP_Konkretisierung/ag_SIP_Konkretisierung_node.html

¹² <https://web.archive.org/web/20250121193206/https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

¹³ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250328183855/https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/coretrustseal-maintenance-wg/activity/>

¹⁴ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250318230000/https://www.dpconline.org/>

¹⁵ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250322102825/https://openpreservation.org/>

¹⁶ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250327082435/https://dcc.ac.uk/>

¹⁷ <https://web.archive.org/web/20241213211836/https://www.uni-due.de/lza/>

Channels

- rdm helpdesks of the community¹⁸
- nestor mailing list¹⁹
- forschungsdaten.org²⁰
- nfdi-list mailing list
- DFN mailinglist forschungsdaten²¹
- talks (e.g. nfdi-talks)
- nfdi-consortia
- set up RocketChat Channel nfdi-lta (rocketchat)
- set up a LTA mailing list on DFN mailing list server

Business models

- Long term funding is necessary
- Digital preservation activities must be located at institutions whose long-term existence is ensured.
- How safe is the data in existing repositories? Trustworthiness of repositories is relevant for digital preservation business models.
- Revisit idea of a LTA basic service in Base4NFDI (RDTraining4NFDI²² as a non-technical service has been accepted as a basic service.

Challenges

- Some challenges of digital preservation, like long term funding, apply also to other topics. Therefore, digital preservation and WG LTA might have a look into respective areas and reuse solutions.

In conclusion, various initiatives, projects and working groups working on preservation of research data or adjacent topics already exist. In consequence, there are possibilities for increasing information exchange, joint work and synergy. This might also be relevant in the context of funding which is a challenge especially for long-term (possibly indefinite) tasks like digital preservation. Trustworthiness of long-term availability of data and of the data service is a question and a need with regard to digital preservation business models.

In order to clarify which consortia are working on which digital preservation solutions already, one possible next step would be to generate an overview of NFDI consortia that are looking into LTA and what their activities and aims are.

¹⁸ For more info:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20250328184635/https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/FDM-Helpdesks>

¹⁹ nestor@langzeitarchivierung.de

²⁰

<https://web.archive.org/web/20221111214249/https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/Langzeitarchivierung>

²¹ forschungsdaten@listserv.dfn.de

²²

<https://web.archive.org/web/20250409082948/https://base4nfdi.de/projects/rdmtraining4nfdi>

Outlook

The workshop highlighted various challenges like missing guidelines and standards (selection criteria, retention times for large data), open questions despite existing best practices and initiatives (software preservation), budget and funding problems (digital preservation in general, personnel for appraisal, long-term storage of large data volumes, long-term responsibility), as well as the challenge of connecting existing initiatives (initiatives and networking).

Practical next steps can be the evaluation of:

- which digital preservation activities already exist in NFDI and which are planned (which has been conducted only in a preliminary manner yet, see Markus et al. 2024),
- which services and institutions have which long-term data preservation responsibilities and
- which kind of research data is not preserved and why.

All three activities rely on awareness of digital preservation standards and generally what digital preservation is.

Furthermore, the WG LTA may initiate or support contact with other initiatives and working groups, pursuing specific topics (e. g. software preservation, selection criteria, data retention and retention times), collecting information and developing recommendations.

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